

101112135 - IDERHA

Integration of heterogeneous Data and Evidence towards Regulatory and HTA Acceptance

WP5 Ethical and legal framework

D5.4 Operational blueprint for regulatory compliance in IDERHA AI developments

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Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the operational blueprint for trustworthy AI development and AI act compliance for IDERHA's platform and the activities that the partners have been performing to develop it. This work has been a cross-Consortium effort that has focused on the advent of new regulations around Artificial Intelligence (AI) and an evolution in trustworthiness expectations around the use of AI in health care provision and individual self-care.

IDERHA finds itself in an unprecedented period of regulatory evolution and greater demand for transparency, accountability and safety that is juxtaposed with a rapid acceleration of technological impact and social uncertainty around information use, reuse and potential. The efforts as documented in this Deliverable have therefore been developed to clarify the position and in a succinct and implementable manner guide and advise the development and deployment teams as to their likely responsibilities and requirements, not just for AI Act compliance, but also for demonstrating trustworthiness to the innovation sector, health care providers, regulators, commissioners and, most importantly, the wider citizenry including patients and research participants.

A multi-method approach has been used to develop the blueprint for compliance. Initially led by Workpackage 6, an engagement strategy about the advent of the AI Act was identified and an educational agenda defined. This resulted in the development of an AI Act Webinar provided by WP5 and WP6, including an overarching contextual framework for the Act's deployment.

The results of the analyses have been to provide a blueprint for trustworthy AI assurance and AI Act compliance as best as IDERHA can ascertain them. The coming twelve months will prove critical for the implementation of these recommendations and the readiness of IDERHA and its solutions for compliance with the latest regulations.

Introduction

This deliverable describes the operational blueprint for trustworthy AI development and AI act compliance for IDERHA's platform and the activities that the partners have been performing to develop it. This work has been a cross Workpackage effort that has focused on the advent of new regulations around AI and an evolution in trustworthiness expectations around the use of AI in health care provision and individual self-care.

The primary focus of this deliverable is on the technical requirements to achieve excellence in regulatory compliance, trustworthiness and transparency. It has been developed in line with the following Deliverables and materials developed around the wider organisational governance and information risk management, including but not limited to Deliverable 5.1 (Framework Data Protection Impact Assessment), Deliverable 5.2 (Code of Conduct and Data Protection Policy), Deliverable 4.1 (Data Management Plan) and Joint Controller Agreement for the full documentary treatise on IDERHA's Processing Activities and their contractual governance across the consortium.

This Deliverable should be viewed as a plan for implementation and will be further enhanced and evolved as the implementation of the compliance requirements proceeds. A fuller review and assessment will occur in the coming 12 months and will be documented in Deliverable 5.5, which focuses on transparency, data quality and bias in the data management and operation of AI driven algorithms.

This Deliverable is structured as follows. It commences with a discussion of the state of regulatory and innovation context within which IDERHA finds itself and continues with a rationale for this deliverable. It then describes the methodology and approach for exploring the key requirements and developing the blueprint. This is followed by a description of the results of the assessments and the blueprint itself. This Deliverable concludes with final reflections and next steps.

Regulatory and Innovation Context

IDERHA finds itself in an unprecedented period of regulatory evolution and greater demand for transparency, accountability and safety that is juxtaposed with a rapid acceleration of technological impact and social uncertainty around personal and sensitive information use, reuse and the need to promote trustworthiness in AI deployment with due regard to safety and fundamental rights. Of particular in August 2024 the AI Act was officially enacted and entered into the European Union official journal. This regulation was drafted to address quality, safety and (in broad terms) fairness and equity for the development and market entry of system driven by AI components.

The enactment of AI regulation occurred within the bounds of significant efforts over the last decade around increasing data protection assurances for organisations that handle information about specific individuals (including the enactment of a General Data Protection Regulation), which occurred during an intensive consideration globally around the ethics of Artificial Intelligence and its use in personal activity as well as state and privately commissioned goods and services.

A result of this effort within the European Union has been the publication of a self-assessment toolkit called the [Assessment List of Trustworthy AI \(ALTAI\)](#) that summarises the European Commission efforts to engage an expert group for developing ethical principles around the ethical use of AI and develop the assessment toolkit.

These efforts produced a broad list of seven requirements focused on:

- Human Agency and Oversight
- Technical Robustness and Safety
- Privacy and Data Governance
- Diversity and non-Discrimination
- Transparency
- Environmental and Societal Wellbeing
- Accountability

These key requirements areas have for the most part been enacted in the requirements of the AI Act itself, where only environmental elements are, arguably, not so clearly defined.

In any event, the alignment between the ALTAI and AI Act are a clear basis upon which to consider the framing requirements and focus points to draw up the compliance blueprint. It should be noted that there is also a wealth of guidelines and standards that have been published and are in development. The most significant of these refer to the CENELEC Standards that are seeking to harmonise existing standards and develop new standards around AI governance and assurance. These are not due for completion until the end of 2025. A deeper review of these standards will form part on the forthcoming Deliverable 5.5 that focuses on assessment frameworks for Data Quality and Bias and will be developed and submitted in 2026.

This point represents the challenge for IDERHA: aside from incomplete standards and guidelines, the reality is that the innovation sector globally does not have a definitive understanding of how the AI Act will be interpreted and implemented in practical terms. It remains unclear how it will be interpreted and align with existing regulations such as the Medical Device Regulation, and it is still unclear as to the state of the development of notifiable authority identification, deployment of sandbox testing environments and the templating of certification evidence for quality control and market authorisation. It is also unclear how the AI Act interpretations will be upheld with regards exemptions, including those around Scientific Research. The European Commission is in the process of developing guidance that will be published later in 2025 that will clarify interpretations thereafter.

The situation is not however unexpected: the European Commission has outlined a timeline for compliance summarised [here](#) by the [Future of Life Institute](#). IDERHA, like many other innovation collaborations, finds itself not in an area of uncertainty, rather a compelling position to help shape what best practice and interpretation might look like in the coming years. IDERHA must balance the need for high standards of protection and quality whilst ensuring that innovation, specifically around AI Algorithm training, is not unnecessarily undermined or stifled due to an unrealistic, overly conservative interpretation of legal requirements that have not yet been formally identified in practical terms.

Rationale for the work outlined in this Deliverable

This efforts as documented in this Deliverable have therefore been developed to clarify the position and in a succinct and implementable manner guide and advise the development and deployment teams as to their likely responsibilities and requirements, not just for AI Act compliance, but also for demonstrating trustworthiness to the innovation sector, health care providers, regulators, commissioners and, most importantly, the wider citizenry including patients and research participants.

In addressing the scope and impact of the AI Act, the working teams looking at AI compliance have considered the status of the applicability of the AI Act, exemptions that may apply and the extent to which they should be considered.

There are two key aspects that are assumed:

- IDERHA's AI driven components are considered a High-Risk AI System

and

- the research exemption does not apply.

These are assumptions of course are open to challenge, but the key deciding factor around seeking to develop a regulatory blueprint that aligns with the AI Act and ALTAI is that without doing so, IDERHA will find itself in an unenviable position towards the end of the project where its options for further sustainability, additional development and product market authorisation will be essentially culled if, at that point, all the work to be done over the next two years would effectively need to be unstitched to apply the quality control, documentation and assurances around the safety and applicability of the tools ahead of any attempt to market authorise. In short, very little could be done with the results, including potentially results publication, without such assurances.

An additional motivation to conduct a deep dive consideration of AI Act implications for the project and its partners was to understand not only the applicability implications, but also to appreciate the responsibilities bestowed upon IDERHA's partners. Following the process as outlined in the Methods section, the working group recognised the importance of understanding the scope of activity within IDERHA and which partners fulfilled the roles defined by the AI Act. Two key roles have been the focus of the work to date:

- the Provider of AI Systems: as per the AI Act definition, this refers to the organisation(s) responsible for the development of AI Models and Algorithm Training for an AI system, and
- the Deployer of AI Systems: specifically, the organisations responsible for taking the AI components and operationalising them within a deployment context, including encapsulating them in software platforms and offering their operation as Software as a Service (SaaS).

Our working group gravitated to these roles in particular, given the wealth of responsibility that is bestowed on them within the AI Act and their clear applicability to IDERHA's partners. The Blueprint specification as described advises on the implications for the role holders, where specific roles will need to be better defined as the work continues.

Methods

A multi-method approach has been used to develop the blueprint for compliance. Initially led by Workpackage 6, an engagement strategy about the advent of the AI Act was identified and an educational agenda defined. This resulted in the development of an AI Act Webinar provided by WP5 and WP6, including an overarching contextual framework for the Act's deployment by WP5 and a legal analysis by WP6. This webinar and slides are available on request.

The webinar was held in May 2024 and it laid the framework for the engagement with the consortium around the AI Act preparations. The working group decided to host a Workshop later in 2024 at the Extended Steering Committee meeting in November that would focus on addressing the key compliance points that could be identified. The outcomes of the Webinar are available on request and the results from the workshop are provided later in this Deliverable.

The working group therefore developed a combined compliance checklist that took the key questions from the ALTAI and the key compliance points from the AI Act (broadly Articles 1-16, with all associated appendices). This helped to outline the questions that will need to be addressed for compliance as best as can be determined at this point.

By agreement the working group summarised the ALTAI criteria and AI Act requirements and divided into the five categories as outlined below:

- Documentation – including Risk Management, System Robustness, General Safety and Technical Documentation;
- Data Quality, Governance and Bias and Representation;
- Algorithm Training and Development Management;
- Transparency – including Traceability, Human Oversight, Communications and Explainability as well as the outline of a Fundamental Rights Impact Assessment.
- Sustainability – specifically the key themes that need to be considered to bring a product or products developed in IDERHA into a marketable result that can reasonably seek market authorisation, including an assessment of Human Agency and Autonomy, Accessibility and Universal Design, Stakeholder Participation, Societal and Environmental Wellbeing and Impact on Work and skills.

Within each, the key assessment questions were articulated and are provided in the Results section. Each category was assigned to a group at the workshop to provide an initial overview of responses, or to help address any questions that arose from participants. The workshop materials, including the categorisations, are available on request.

The responses from the groups helped to address some of the points that were raised in the assessment questions. This allowed the working group to conduct a deeper dive into the assessment materials, but also to expand out the more technical aspects and do a more thorough treatise on the AI Act requirements. This has been further enhanced by the [EMA reflection paper on the use of Artificial Intelligence \(AI\) in the medicinal product lifecycle](#) and the [CNIL guidelines for the development of AI Systems](#) where lifecycle and risk management are concerned. The resulting details have been specified in the results section below.

Results: Detailed Blueprint Specification

The results of the work have been encapsulated in a table that represents the assessment questions for the compliance groups and their requirements, the source of the requirements (i.e. the specific section of the AI Act, the ALTAI Assessment Checklist and specific criterion, or the Workshop Assessments), the parties responsible for addressing them (by Workpackage), where they apply (i.e. for developers, deployers, regulatory teams etc., and when they are due (i.e. whether this is ongoing throughout the lifetime of IDERHA or for market authorisation only). The key materials are the Response to the assessment questions as well

as a gap analysis of what needs to be implemented for compliance. There are also a series of Guidelines for IDERHA personnel to follow, which will be added to the IDERHA Code of Conduct and Data Protection Policy.

A full version of the results is available at the IDERHA SharePoint site, where a summary of the tables including the assessment questions for groups and requirements, the responses and items to implement for compliance are listed below according to each group and sub-category of as outlined in the methods section.

Documentation – including Risk Management, System Robustness, General Safety and Technical Documentation

The tables that follow in this section focus in the documentation requirements that the AI Act and Trustworthy AI expectations introduce. The first set refer specifically at the risk management approaches that are required and their documentation, and how IDERHA has been tackling these and will adapt its approach to achieve compliance.

DOCUMENTATION: RISK MANAGEMENT

Table 1: Risk Management Criteria

Risk Management Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
<p>1. A risk management system shall be established, implemented, documented and maintained in relation to high-risk AI systems.</p>	<p>The risk management of for the project is multi-fold. It includes the data protection compliance and risk management, ethical and research governance risk management, project completion risk management and tooling development and risk management</p>	<p>This is an ongoing activity. xxx</p>
<p>2. The risk management system shall be understood as a continuous iterative process planned and run throughout the entire lifecycle of a high-risk AI system, requiring regular systematic review and updating. It shall comprise the following steps:</p>	<p>The risk management approach will rely on a detailed description of the lifecycle of the AI Systems from their training and development, ongoing monitoring and any updates and retraining. The focus initially is on the development process where a preliminary lifecycle can be agreed upon. The risk management system can then iterate over this using any existing risk management. This is primarily around the information risk management via the DPIA and DMP. It is unlikely that this will require any amendments to ethics approvals but will be a matter for ongoing oversight of the advisory boards.</p>	<p>Map out the system lifecycle from data gathering, through model development, training, implementation, deployment and use.</p>

Risk Management Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
<p>(a) the identification and analysis of the known and the reasonably foreseeable risks that the high-risk AI system can pose to health, safety or fundamental rights when the high-risk AI system is used in accordance with its intended purpose;</p>	<p>The existing list of risks as identified via research governance overarches the health and safety risks. Further issues may be discovered or considered as the tool is developed and this should work within the study execution protocol and recording of identified risks or serious adverse events</p>	<p>This is an ongoing matter and established within the Framework for the conduct of studies. A reporting mechanism for identified risks could be updated via the lifecycle mapping. Additionally a Fundamental Rights Impact Assessment (FRIA) can be helpful here. It should be further noted that any risk mitigation methods that have been used, including vi the DPIA and DMP processes, should also incorporate a wider consideration around personal data and data that is not personal – i.e. further to any anonymised data but also around statistical analyses keyed to model generation and algorithm training</p>
<p>(b) the estimation and evaluation of the risks that may emerge when the high-risk AI system is used in accordance with its intended purpose, and under conditions of reasonably foreseeable misuse;</p>	<p>As above as the framing point, but any risks should be quantified using established metrics (i.e. threat, impact and likelihood analysis)</p>	<p>A risk quantification framework that can be adapted from the existing risk management profile in the DPIA</p>
<p>(c) the evaluation of other risks possibly arising, based on the analysis of data gathered from the post-market monitoring system referred to in Article 72;</p>	<p>We can establish an evaluation framework during the project lifetime in anticipation of market authorisation</p>	<p>A risk quantification framework that can be adapted from the existing risk management profile in the DPIA</p>

Risk Management Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
<p>(d) the adoption of appropriate and targeted risk management measures designed to address the risks identified pursuant to point (a).</p>	<p>We can establish an evaluation framework during the project lifetime in anticipation of market authorisation</p>	<p>A risk quantification framework that can be adapted from the existing risk management profile in the DPIA</p>
<p>3. The risks referred to in this Article shall concern only those which may be reasonably mitigated or eliminated through the development or design of the high-risk AI system, or the provision of adequate technical information.</p>	<p>This scopes the items related to the risk management process in items 1 and 2.</p>	<p>A review of identified risks and updates to this with regards AI Use. A FRIA will assist with this.</p>
<p>4. The risk management measures referred to in point (d) above, shall give due consideration to the effects and possible interaction resulting from the combined application of the requirements set out in this Section, with a view to minimising risks more effectively while achieving an appropriate balance in implementing the measures to fulfil those requirements.</p>	<p>This scopes the items related to the risk management processes above in point 2.</p>	<p>A review of identified risks and updates to this with regards AI Use. A FRIA will assist with this.</p>
<p>5. The risk management measures referred to in paragraph 2, point (d), shall be such that the relevant residual risk associated with each hazard, as well as the overall residual risk of the high-risk AI systems is judged to be acceptable. In identifying the most appropriate risk management measures, the following shall be ensured:</p>	<p>This scopes the items related to the risk management processes above in point 2.</p>	<p>A review of identified risks and updates to this with regards AI Use. A FRIA will assist with this. We should consider acceptance levels where this is not already clear.</p>

Risk Management Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
(a) elimination or reduction of risks identified and evaluated pursuant to paragraph 2 in as far as technically feasible through adequate design and development of the high-risk AI system;	This scopes the items related to the risk management processes above in point 2.	
(b) where appropriate, implementation of adequate mitigation and control measures addressing risks that cannot be eliminated;	This scopes the items related to the risk management processes above in point 2.	This will need a reconciliation of existing risks and mitigation measures as per the DPIA and DMP. Updates may be needed.
(c) provision of information required pursuant to Article 13 and, where appropriate, training to deployers. With a view to eliminating or reducing risks related to the use of the high-risk AI system, due consideration shall be given to the technical knowledge, experience, education, the training to be expected by the deployer, and the presumable context in which the system is intended to be used.	This is an important aspect for training and education across the consortium that must work alongside individual partner activities in this space.	Ongoing adaptation of outreach and engagement measures
6. High-risk AI systems shall be tested for the purpose of identifying the most appropriate and targeted risk management measures. Testing shall ensure that high-risk AI systems perform consistently for their intended purpose and that they are in compliance with the requirements set out in this Section.	The risk management process for conducting a study involving live participants forms a large part of this. Further consideration should be given over any emergent or novel challenges presented by the algorithms	Addressed via existing frameworks for risk management

Risk Management Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
<p>7. Testing procedures may include testing in real-world conditions in accordance with Article 60.</p>	<p>Testing procedures have been established in line with the study protocol and DMP, working in the DPIA aspects as well. This will need to evolve towards the Sandbox requirements as well as further real-world testing, though this will evolve with the study and tooling development scenarios in line with existing legislation</p>	<p>Likely a gap analysis between study infrastructure and emerging standards for sandboxes and live testing environments. It is unlikely that these will differ significantly as to the standards to which the project is adhering to already, though this will be monitored throughout. The lifecycle mapping will also support this evolution and present any changes that are needed for adapting procedures and environments</p>
<p>8. The testing of high-risk AI systems shall be performed, as appropriate, at any time throughout the development process, and, in any event, prior to their being placed on the market or put into service. Testing shall be carried out against prior defined metrics and probabilistic thresholds that are appropriate to the intended purpose of the high-risk AI system.</p>	<p>See item 7</p>	<p>See item 7</p>
<p>9. When implementing the risk management system as provided for in paragraphs 1 to 7, providers shall give consideration to whether in view of its intended purpose the high-risk AI system is likely to have an adverse impact on persons under the age of 18 and, as appropriate, other vulnerable groups.</p>	<p>This has been accounted for as part of the research governance and safety approaches considered for IDERHA's associated studies, which are independently approved by local research ethics committees.</p>	<p>This will need to be considered as any IDERHA solution moves outside of a research study context and into pre market authorisation. This should also be reviewed if the models become general purpose</p>

Risk Management Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
10. For providers of high-risk AI systems that are subject to requirements regarding internal risk management processes under other relevant provisions of Union law, the aspects provided in paragraphs 1 to 9 may be part of, or combined with, the risk management procedures established pursuant to that law.	This is the main point for this section - the risk management is overlaid with study conduct via research governance requirements as established in the Study Protocols.	Ongoing oversight and adaptation as the studies progress in line with existing approaches and processes
What kind of external guidance or third-party auditing processes to oversee ethical concerns and accountability measures do you need? What further guidance would you like to see?	It would be wise to keep abreast of wider guidelines and standards that are developed by the European Commission and regulatory authorities as well as CENELEC, though the existing independent bodies within IDERHA are very useful and should be leveraged more clearly	Horizon scanning for further advisory and guidance. It is clear that Developers will need guidance internally from the project
Do you foresee the need for involvement of any third parties within and beyond the development phase?	Not as of yet - this may change nearer product authorisation after the end of IDERHA	
Beyond the workshops, should IDERHA organise risk training and, if so, should it go beyond the potential legal framework applicable to the AI system?	Further workshops have been scheduled, specifically exploring the roles defined within the AI Act and their implications for IDERHA. The Workshops are scheduled for May the Annual Consortium Meeting	N/A
In addition to the Ethics, Patient and Clinical Advisory Boards, do you think IDERHA should establish an AI ethics review board or a similar mechanism to discuss the overall accountability and ethics practices, including potential unclear grey areas?	N/A	N/A
Should we establish a process to discuss and continuously monitor and assess the AI system's adherence to this Assessment List for Trustworthy AI (ALTAI)?	This needs to be aligned with the specification of the AI System Lifecycle and the update the DMP Periodically	Lifecycle Specification

Risk Management Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
This might include processes to identify and document any conflicts between the 6 aforementioned requirements or between different ethical principles and explanation of the 'trade-off' decisions made.	See above.	See above.
Think also about any appropriate training to those involved in such a process in addition to the legal framework applicable to the AI system	Plenary Workshops as described	N/A
What process should IDERHA establish for third parties (e.g. suppliers, end-users, subjects, distributors/vendors or workers) to report potential vulnerabilities, risks or biases in the AI system?	This relates primarily to the onboarding of new partners for data sharing. This follows a risk management approach established by running the DPIA and updating the DMP, as well as onboarding of new partners to the Joint Controller Agreement. These steps provide a basis for risk mitigation and reporting of any potential issues.	Review of onboarding processes and adding of process details for reporting vulnerabilities and risks to onboarding requirements that parties must adhere to.
Bear in mind this should foster revision of the risk management process where needed	See above.	See above.
For applications that can adversely affect individuals, have redress by design mechanisms been considered for implementation?	This is part of the development and study work. Any particular issues, clinical or otherwise, will be logged s part of feedback from participants and assessment of the tool and its impact.	Ongoing Monitoring of participant experience

QUALITY MANAGEMENT

The next set of criteria considered under Table 2 relate to quality management processes and their documentation, as described below.

Table 2: Quality Management Criteria

Quality Management Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
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<p>What are the quality management systems in place for IDERHA?</p>	<p>During the workshop, it has been clarified that under IDERHA there is no suitable legal entity to host a Quality Management System for the AI systems. Recommended topic for discussion which will influence certification decisions. Each partner does however hold a responsibility to address their existing risk management responsibilities, including participant safety, ethical adherence, information risk management. These processes are already in place and may need to be evolved for AI Compliance</p>	<p>Categorisation and cataloguing of risk management processes in place currently and any gaps to this</p>
<p>Will they cover the AI processes as outlined in the previous questions?</p>	<p>There needs to be a gap analysis for each of the quality measures in place to see whether they are missing any AI specific items. This is ongoing work for WP5.</p>	<p>Gap Analysis of quality measures and how they will evolve.</p>
<p>Do you foresee any gaps:</p>		
<p>E.g. Data Management Quality Systems Requirements might not be in place</p>	<p>Likely this will fall to a need to better assess bias in data and eventual bias in decision making.</p>	<p>Ongoing review of data quality aspects will occur. This will be aligned with efforts across related projects to consider shared understanding of the developing requirements.</p>
<p>If there are none, what are the first steps to introduce them?</p>	<p>The existing Quality Management Systems need to be evolved.</p>	<p>Discuss and define a suitable entity as part of IDERHA's Sustainability Plans to eventually host the Project outputs in the future and the Quality Management System as appropriate but in the first instance develop a catalogue of the Quality Management Systems</p>

Could be more clear that a new theme starts here

System Robustness - Resilience to Attack: Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
<p>Could the AI system have adversarial, critical or damaging effects (e.g. to human or societal safety) in case of risks or threats such as design or technical faults, defects, outages, attacks, misuse, inappropriate or malicious use?</p>	<p>This has been assessed and is continually assessed under the work done for the DPIA and specification in the DMP. Additionally the updates are developed as part of the deployment of the tooling across the different components as well as the individual partners responsible for each part of the overall system. There is a risk of adversarial and wider damage for all the elements outlined. Some of the design elements and data quality assessments help to mitigate this. The focus is on WP1 for the deployment assessments and risk management.</p>	<p>This is ongoing oversight and has been documented in the DPIA and DMP, which needs to be continuously Updated</p>
<p>Will the Platform and the AI system be certified for cybersecurity (e.g. the certification scheme created by the Cybersecurity Act in Europe) or is it compliant with specific security standards?</p>	<p>This will remain under the power and decision making of the individual partners to enforce. A registry of the certifications will need to be kept, where some partners work within a risk managed framework including Cyber certification and ISO 27000 series, Hospital sites will be certified to hold their clinical data. WP1 will likely need to provide the discourse around standards compliance as part of the deployment operations</p>	<p>Develop a catalogue of certifications</p>
<p>How exposed is the AI system to cyber-attacks?</p>	<p>This remains in the framework of governance and risk management for the project partners in particular</p>	<p>Review the risk management and analysis in the DMP.</p>
<p>Will we assess potential forms of attacks to which the AI system could be vulnerable?</p>	<p>This is ongoing as part of the project wide and individual partner risk management responsibility and activity.</p>	<p>Review DMP to ensure this is up to date after DPIA is updated. This can be considered by the Data Security Task Force</p>
<p>How will we consider different types of vulnerabilities and potential entry points for attacks such as:</p>	<p>These points need to be addressed primarily by WP1 with reference to WP2, WP3 and WP5. It will relate back to risk management within the DPIA process overall.</p>	<p>This can also be addressed by the Data Security Task Force.</p>

System Robustness - Resilience to Attack: Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
Data poisoning (i.e. manipulation of training data);		
Model evasion (i.e. classifying the data according to the attacker's will);		
Model inversion (i.e. infer the model parameters)		
How do we plan to put measures in place to ensure the integrity, robustness and overall security of the AI system against potential attacks over its lifecycle?	This will continue to be built on the established risk management process for data protection and compliance as described under that section	We need to catalogue more clearly our risk management approach with regards a gap analysis of anything that we need for the AI systems. Bias, misrepresentation and the specific risks above need to be addressed.
Will we penetration test the platform?	This will be for each of the IDERHA partners to decide - likely it will fall to WP1 lead on the specification and requirement.	We must log any penetration testing that partners have performed

System Robustness - Resilience to Attack: Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
<p>How will we inform end-users of the duration of security coverage and updates?</p>	<p>This is a difficult point to answer as the systems are being developed by different partners and each will need to be responsible for updating any system change and security details. WP1 will likely take the lead on this.</p> <p>This is for system deployment primarily, only in the hospitals will deploy it. ML Updates are not easy to do because you have to have additional datasets or other validation material and not easy in RWE patient data. Shared with deployers primarily. As providers WP2 is for ML models that will sit inside of a toolset. Form Software Engineering is a company will use Data Scientists and researchers. There are also those who will integrate with a wider platform. This is for WP1 and UNILUX is planning infrastructure. Not familiar with Machine learning models. Nobody yet for integration. WP1 handles deployment. We will need to explore this and ask WP1 teams and they are nearer the integration task and Phillips as well have a tool development analysing imaging tasks.</p>	<p>A list of security updates will need to be kept.</p>
<p>What length is the expected timeframe within which you provide security updates for the Platform?</p>	<p>This matter will need to be agreed with the consortium partners, with WP1 colleagues hosting the platforms providing details of their routine management of their infrastructure and planned deployments.</p>	<p>Their needs to be a balance between routine software updates and levels of details shared. Likely a regular update is most appropriate and will be determined by WP1, or in the event of a breach that will need to be addressed.</p>

GENERAL SAFETY

This section represented by table 3 relates to the how IDERHA is approaching the general safety of the algorithms and systems as they are deployed

Table 3: General Safety

General Safety Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
<p>1. High-risk AI systems shall technically allow for the automatic recording of events (logs) over the lifetime of the system.</p>	<p>Logging facilities will need to be configured so that details of decisions made by the algorithms, which data was used to inform the decision and what the outcome of the decision was (i.e. directed to a particular identification, risk prediction or piece of advice) was made. This will also need to relate to the onboarding of data, its processing, the generation of models and the data used to train an algorithm. Additionally, logging of whether a user accepted or rejected a decision will also need to be recorded and made available. Note that the specifics include the points under 1(a) of Annex III of the AI Act, specifically: recording of the period of each use of the system (start date and time and end date and time of each use); the reference database against which input data has been checked by the system; the input data for which the search has led to a match; the identification of the natural persons involved in the verification of the results. Broadly this falls to WP1, WP2 and WP3 with oversight and support from WP5 and, where needed, WP6 and WP8.</p>	<p>An assessment of workflows needs to be performed so that the point of logging features can be mapped and logging configured according to available features.</p>
<p>2. In order to ensure a level of traceability of the functioning of a high-risk AI system that is appropriate to the intended purpose of the system, logging capabilities shall enable the recording of events relevant for:</p>		<p>One tool under development for GDPR compliance may be appropriate once updated with AI Act requirements as outlined below. See https://elixir.pages.uni.lu/daisy-doc/</p>

General Safety Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
(a) identifying situations that may result in the high-risk AI system presenting a risk within the meaning of Article 79(1) or in a substantial modification;	Article 79(1) is unlikely to be applicable to the IDERHA solutions.	
(b) facilitating the post-market monitoring referred to in Article 72; and	The logging should try to meet the requirements for post market authorisations	This is not immediately clear and has not been specified yet
(c) monitoring the operation of high-risk AI systems referred to in Article 26(5).	This has been outlined above	
3. For high-risk AI systems referred to in point 1 (a), of Annex III, the logging capabilities shall provide, at a minimum:	These items are specific requirements as per the assessment requirements. These are picked up in the general recommendations	
(a) recording of the period of each use of the system (start date and time and end date and time of each use);		One tool under development for GDPR compliance may be appropriate once updated with AI Act requirements as outlined below. See https://elixir.pages.uni.lu/daisy-doc/
(b) the reference database against which input data has been checked by the system;		
(c) the input data for which the search has led to a match;		
(d) the identification of the natural persons involved in the verification of the results, as referred to in Article 14(5).	Article 14(5) refers to decision identification confirmation from the system by at least two natural persons with the necessary competence, training and authority. This remains mostly in the remit of WP3.	It is not immediately clear what would determine authority, competence and training at the moment

General Safety Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
How will we define risks, risk metrics and risk levels of the AI system in each specific use case?	Much of this has been articulated in the DPIA and documented in the DMP in terms of mitigation strategies. These should be updated iteratively as the specific operation of the AI components is specified in more details and the deployment is better understood and defined.	A DPIA Review should be performed to ensure that any specific risks recently identified in the AI Act and ALTAI
Did you put in place a process to continuously measure and assess risks?	The existing risk management measures will need to be established based upon the lifecycle specification	
Did you inform end-users and subjects of existing or potential risks?	This has been outlined in the protocol and informed consent form.	Additional effort will need to be made to provide risk descriptions to project partner users.
How will we the possible threats to the AI system (design faults, technical faults, environmental threats) and the possible consequences?	This will rely on the update to existing processes that are in place for development monitoring and study conduct. Partly for WP1. We need to consider threats and their type and define their roles. These can be addressed by AI Providers and by AI deployers, and by data source IT departments. One example a design fault has some undocumented biases and that needs to be addressed that would be something for the AI developers. Technical faults could be software developers who have embedded these AI models have bugs that they need to address. Environment is more service providers, cloud services used and so forth.	Refer to Lifecycle and Cataloging recommendations
Will we assess the risk of possible malicious use, misuse or inappropriate use of the AI system?	This will need to be assessed via a FRIA	Conduct a FRIA - a template is underway.

General Safety Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
Will we define safety criticality levels (e.g. related to human integrity) of the possible consequences of faults or misuse of the AI system?	This is already (loosely) defined in the Protocol.	We will need to map the boundaries of safety critical aspects as the platform is fully developed.
Who will we assess the dependency of a critical AI system's decisions on its stable and reliable behaviour?	This is likely a clinical matter and should be decided by clinical advisory.	This should be in place within the protocol but may need to be further developed and enhanced.
Did you align the reliability/testing requirements to the appropriate levels of stability and reliability?	This is likely a clinical matter and should be decided by clinical advisory.	This should be in place within the protocol but may need to be further developed and enhanced
How will we plan fault tolerance via, e.g. a duplicated system or another parallel system (AI-based or 'conventional')?	This is likely a clinical matter and should be decided by clinical advisory.	This should be in place within the protocol but may need to be further developed and enhanced
Will we develop a mechanism to evaluate when the AI system has been changed to merit a new review of its technical robustness and safety?	This will need to be agreed across stakeholders - this should likely fall to a routine update as per existing risk management processes in place.	This relates to the lifecycle specification.

TECHNICAL DOCUMENTATION

Table 4 below provides details of IDERHA's technical documentation and implementation requirements for compliance as the project proceeds.

Table 4: Technical Documentation Criteria

Technical Documentation Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
1. Providers of high-risk AI systems shall put a quality management system in place that ensures compliance with this Regulation. That system shall be documented in a systematic and orderly manner in the form of written policies, procedures and instructions, and shall include at least the following aspects:	Please refer to the details described under quality management. Further Updates are below.	

Technical Documentation Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
(a) a strategy for regulatory compliance, including compliance with conformity assessment procedures and procedures for the management of modifications to the high-risk AI system;	This is currently managed via the DPIA process for routine review, the DMP update procedure and the Research Governance oversight and review.	Consideration within these frameworks will need to be given around model generation, aggregated data and statistical analyses keyed to algorithm development.
(b) techniques, procedures and systematic actions to be used for the design, design control and design verification of the high-risk AI system;	This will rely on the Developer teams to document their procedures for data acquisition, processing, algorithm training after model development.	Refer to the Cataloguing Recommendations
(c) techniques, procedures and systematic actions to be used for the development, quality control and quality assurance of the high-risk AI system;	As above but will also include data quality and bias assessments	
(d) examination, test and validation procedures to be carried out before, during and after the development of the high-risk AI system, and the frequency with which they have to be carried out;	This relies on a clear documentation of testing procedures and practice as defined by the developers and the infrastructure providers for the test environments	Refer to the Cataloguing Recommendations
(e) technical specifications, including standards, to be applied and, where the relevant harmonised standards are not applied in full or do not cover all of the relevant requirements set out in Section 2, the means to be used to ensure that the high-risk AI system complies with those requirements;	This will rely on the Developer teams to document technical specifications of their processes for model generation, algorithm training and integration with the wider platform.	Refer to the Cataloguing Recommendations

Technical Documentation Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
(f) systems and procedures for data management, including data acquisition, data collection, data analysis, data labelling, data storage, data filtration, data mining, data aggregation, data retention and any other operation regarding the data that is performed before and for the purpose of the placing on the market or the putting into service of high-risk AI systems;	Much of this has already been put into place with regards the information risk management, DPIA and the DMP. Additional details will need to be logged around the data management and transfer around the evidence of the activity of the system prior to market authorisation. These details will need to be retained.	Refer to recommendations on risk assessing against analyses data derived from personal data processing.
(g) the risk management system referred to in Article 9;	Described under Risk Management above.	
(h) the setting-up, implementation and maintenance of a post-market monitoring system, in accordance with Article 72;	The current processes must be documented so that they can inform this process description once the specific requirements have been provided by the authorities (likely August 2025).	
(i) procedures related to the reporting of a serious incident in accordance with Article 73;	The current processes must be documented so that they can inform this process description once the specific requirements have been provided by the authorities (likely August 2025).	
(j) the handling of communication with national competent authorities, other relevant authorities, including those providing or supporting the access to data, notified bodies, other operators, customers or other interested parties;	The current processes must be documented so that they can inform this process description once the specific requirements have been provided by the authorities (likely August 2025).	
(k) systems and procedures for record-keeping of all relevant documentation and information;	Much of this has already been put into place with regards the information risk management, DPIA and the DMP.	Much if this has already been defined but needs to be better articulated with reference to key documents and accountability processes

Technical Documentation Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
(l) resource management, including security-of-supply related measures;	This will be part of the sustainability discussions when a minimum viable product has been implemented (at least for assessment purposes). Currently the following is not strictly the same management but the articulation of responsibilities and funding for the Description of Action may seem relevant here.	
(m) an accountability framework setting out the responsibilities of the management and other staff with regard to all the aspects listed in this paragraph.	This will be part of the sustainability discussions when a minimum viable product has been implemented (at least for assessment purposes). Currently the following is not strictly the same management but the articulation of responsibilities and funding for the Description of Action may seem relevant here. This will go back to the Consortium Agreement, the Joint Controller Agreement and the Data Management Plan, as well as the DPIA	
From the AI Act Annex IV and Article 11, do any of the following pose a challenge?		
A general description of the AI system including:	There is no issue with completing this, much of it is on the Website, in the consent and information leaflets as well as publicly available material. This will be further articulated within a FRIA as well as the Cataloguing Recommendations.	A concise description should be drafted.
(a) its intended purpose, the name of the provider and the version of the system reflecting its relation to previous versions;	There is no issue with completing this, much of it is on the Website, in the consent and information leaflets as well as publicly available material. This will be further articulated within a FRIA as well as the Cataloguing Recommendations.	A concise description should be drafted.
(b) how the AI system interacts with, or can be used to interact with, hardware or software, including with other AI systems, that are not part of the AI system itself, where applicable;	There is no issue with completing this, much of it is on the Website, in the consent and information leaflets as well as publicly available material. This will be further articulated within a FRIA as well as the Cataloguing Recommendations.	A concise description should be drafted.

Technical Documentation Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
(c) the versions of relevant software or firmware, and any requirements related to version updates;	This may already be documented but a registry of the software being used will need to be compiled. See Cataloguing Recommendations	This will be met by establishing a library of software and hardware tools across partners with the details as specified
(d) the description of all the forms in which the AI system is placed on the market or put into service, such as software packages embedded into hardware, downloads, or APIs;	The current processes must be documented so that they can inform this process description once the specific requirements have been provided by the authorities (likely August 2025).	
(e) the description of the hardware on which the AI system is intended to run;	As above.	
(f) where the AI system is a component of products, photographs or illustrations showing external features, the marking and internal layout of those products;	As above,	
(g) a basic description of the user-interface provided to the deployer;	This has already been done for the Citizen App but will still need some work for the risk prediction and self-reporting tools most likely. Refer to the Cataloguing recommendations for more details. This will relate to the App work in Asklepios	
(h) instructions for use for the deployer, and a basic description of the user-interface provided to the deployer, where applicable;	A concise instructions manual should be drafted across all components of the system. There is no issue with completing this, though the technical specifications and process flow diagrams will be a firm foundation for articulating a narrative in this case and the development of technical specifications, operation of the components and how they should themselves be operated. Refer to the Cataloguing Recommendations.	

Technical Documentation Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
Will we have a detailed description of the elements of the AI system and of the process for its development?		
This includes the entire data flow lifecycle and how the Platform handles it	Refer to Comments around the need to document the system lifecycle across the different components. This should relate to the development of models and algorithm training, their update and how this in turn impacts other components. Monitoring and further growth of the algorithms also need to be addressed, how these will be assessed and reassessed and how any additional data addition, manipulation or feature development may impact the operation of the AI and the components that it connects to.	
It also includes monitoring of operation, change management and details of evaluations conducted	This relates to the record keeping and operational logging. The description of the system operation will help to define this better in terms of documentation	
2. A detailed description of the elements of the AI system and of the process for its development, including:		
(a) the methods and steps performed for the development of the AI system, including, where relevant, recourse to pre-trained systems or tools provided by third parties and how those were used, integrated or modified by the provider;	This will be served by existing data flow diagrams and process flow specifications, where more detail will be needed to describe the process of learning. More detail for the DMP and DPIA may be required around referral to pretrained models and other data sources	

Technical Documentation Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
<p>(b) the design specifications of the system, namely the general logic of the AI system and of the algorithms; the key design choices including the rationale and assumptions made, including with regard to persons or groups of persons in respect of who, the system is intended to be used; the main classification choices; what the system is designed to optimise for, and the relevance of the different parameters; the description of the expected output and output quality of the system; the decisions about any possible trade-off made regarding the technical solutions adopted to comply with the requirements set out in Chapter III, Section 2;</p>	<p>This will be readily deployable as part of the manual and system description updates where the specifications of the system are a lower level, deeper and more detailed representation of the higher-level narratives described under other Annex IV requirements above.</p>	
<p>(c) the description of the system architecture explaining how software components build on or feed into each other and integrate into the overall processing; the computational resources used to develop, train, test and validate the AI system;</p>	<p>This will be readily deployable as part of the manual and system description updates where the specifications of the system are a lower level, deeper and more detailed representation of the higher-level narratives described under other Annex IV requirements above.</p>	
<p>(d) where relevant, the data requirements in terms of datasheets describing the training methodologies and techniques and the training data sets used, including a general description of these data sets, information about their provenance, scope and main characteristics; how the data was obtained and selected; labelling procedures (e.g. for supervised learning), data cleaning methodologies (e.g. outliers' detection);</p>	<p>This will relate to the details in the DMP around the specification of data sources and quality assessments, as well as the required description of the data handling and use as defined above by the developers when they handle the data for model generation and training.</p>	

Technical Documentation Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
<p>(e) assessment of the human oversight measures needed in accordance with Article 14, including an assessment of the technical measures needed to facilitate the interpretation of the outputs of AI systems by the deployers, in accordance with Article 13(3), point (d);</p>	<p>This is discussed under Human Agency and Oversight for the ALTAI. WP2 can provide a detailed description of the AI Models' performance in terms of metrics, evaluation on external test sets and so forth. The shape of these is that they write a scientific publication which is thoroughly peer reviewed and can be considered a protocol for the evaluation of the algorithm. See draft of use case once the use case of draft. They have a study protocol of the modelling and the evaluation plan. These frame the approach, and they are in the SharePoint and only shareable within the consortium under WP3 Deliverables. That is about handling documents and planning as well as providing access, WP2 is implementation</p>	
<p>(f) where applicable, a detailed description of pre-determined changes to the AI system and its performance, together with all the relevant information related to the technical solutions adopted to ensure continuous compliance of the AI system with the relevant requirements set out in Chapter III, Section 2;</p>	<p>Predetermined changes are not likely relevant</p>	
<p>(g) the validation and testing procedures used, including information about the validation and testing data used and their main characteristics; metrics used to measure accuracy, robustness and compliance with other relevant requirements set out in Chapter III, Section 2, as well as potentially discriminatory impacts; test logs and all test reports dated and signed by the responsible persons, including with regard to predetermined changes as referred to under point (f);</p>	<p>The testing process and particulars, including validation, must be better defined and integrated with existing testing efforts. This relates to the specifications for testing and validation metrics described above, as well as the lifecycle of the system and the impact on other components. Data Handling and particulars must be carefully noted and documented.</p>	

Technical Documentation Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
(h) cybersecurity measures put in place;	As per DMP, which will need to be updated	
3. Detailed information about the monitoring, functioning and control of the AI system, in particular with regard to: its capabilities and limitations in performance, including the degrees of accuracy for specific persons or groups of persons on which the system is intended to be used and the overall expected level of accuracy in relation to its intended purpose; the foreseeable unintended outcomes and sources of risks to health and safety, fundamental rights and discrimination in view of the intended purpose of the AI system; the human oversight measures needed in accordance with Article 14, including the technical measures put in place to facilitate the interpretation of the outputs of AI systems by the deployers; specifications on input data, as appropriate;	The starting point is the conduct of the study in its current form. The monitoring and management of the AI system steps have only been defined as part of the Study Protocols and intended deployment scenarios. These will need further development and implementation as the pathways are discovered. This will relate to monitoring an observation as the tool is evaluated but a real-world deployment scenario is also developed.	
4. A description of the appropriateness of the performance metrics for the specific AI system;	See above for the description about identification of metrics and levels of acceptability - appropriateness of the metrics need to be described	
5. A detailed description of the risk management system in accordance with Article 9;	As described above under Risk Management	
6. A description of relevant changes made by the provider to the system through its lifecycle;	As above - relies on mapping out the lifecycle and applicable updates, as well as monitoring	

Technical Documentation Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
7. A list of the harmonised standards applied in full or in part the references of which have been published in the Official Journal of the European Union; where no such harmonised standards have been applied, a detailed description of the solutions adopted to meet the requirements set out in Chapter III, Section 2, including a list of other relevant standards and technical specifications applied;	Note the harmonised standards are mostly still in development and will not be published until the end of the year. A catalogue of these should be kept detailing the standard in play, where it has been applied, any certifications in place and any that are likely to be sought	
8. A copy of the EU declaration of conformity referred to in Article 47;	The current processes must be documented so that they can inform this process description once the specific requirements have been provided by the authorities (likely August 2025).	
9. A detailed description of the system in place to evaluate the AI system performance in the post-market phase in accordance with Article 72, including the post-market monitoring plan referred to in Article 72(3).	The current processes must be documented so that they can inform this process description once the specific requirements have been provided by the authorities (likely August 2025).	

Data Quality, Governance and Bias and Representation

The next group focussed on Data Quality, Governance, Bias and Representation. Arguably significant work has already been achieved for data governance compliance as outlined below. Wider requirements exist as specified for quality assessments, bias and representation considerations.

DATA GOVERNANCE

Table 5: Data Governance Criteria

Data Governance Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
Is our AI system being trained, or was it developed, by using or processing personal data (including special categories of personal data)?	Both scenarios apply. Personal data will be processed at Data Provider Sites to make them available for machine learning, model generation and then training. This will include any de-identification processes that are applied	Detailed documentation on the source and provenance of the data. Includes the DMP, local site ROPAs. This needs to be recorded for all stages of data use including data preparation, training, data input (user input) and fine tuning. This relies on a Lifecycle for data use as well as system development.
What measures is IDERHA putting in place to meet the following measures some of which are mandatory under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), or a non-European equivalent?	The process has applied the data protection by design and default approach as outlined by GDPR. Detailed responses are below	DPIA framework - already underway. The DPIA will need to be reviewed and adapted to assess AI specific Risks, Data Storage considerations, and is currently being reviewed to that end as part of the template evolution to meet AI Act, ALTAI and Data Quality related requirements. These will align more with the data and system Lifecycle specifications that have been recommended.
Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA);		DPIA framework - already underway
Designate a Data Protection Officer (DPO) and include them at an early state in the development, procurement or use phase of the AI system;	All DPO details have been provided and are stored by the Project on the SharePoint	N/A

Data Governance Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
Oversight security mechanisms for data processing (including limiting access to qualified personnel, mechanisms for logging data access and making modifications);	The data processing oversight is documented under the DPIA, Data Flow Diagrams and DMP. All processing, activities, authorisations and procedural aspects are documented here.	It is likely the further details around logging need to be addressed. This should be picked up under the record keeping points as addressed under Documentation
Measures to achieve privacy-by-design and default (e.g. transparency, encryption, pseudonymisation, aggregation, anonymisation);	Solutions have been documented under the DPIA, DMP and will be further reviewed as the documentation elements are updated	The DPIA needs to be updated to consider the latest DMP and new AI Requirements
Data minimisation, in particular personal data (including special categories of data);	The minimisation justifications have been confirmed or are being confirmed by Research Ethics Committees at local sites. The data needed to conduct the studies and train the AI has been articulated to the sites and the Ethics Committees	This will be an ongoing process where it may be the case that data minimisation has hampered the completeness of the data and / or introduced a bias and should be monitored. This relates to transparency as well, and has implications for handling data under the lawful basis of consent, and for obtaining consent in the first place. This will need to be carefully articulated (not just for the studies under IDERHA, but also any future system market entry and use).
Did you implement the right to withdraw consent, the right to object and the right to be forgotten into the development of the AI system?	Yes - as stipulated by the protocol, consent forms and ethics approvals. Where existing data sets are being used this will be pursuant to the consents already provided (though arguably the data subjects are not able to opt out necessarily...	Check that procedures for withdrawal work as expected.

Data Governance Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
Did you consider the privacy and data protection implications and risks of data collected, generated or processed over the course of the AI system's life cycle?	Arguably the DPIA and DMP, as well as the Research Ethics only go so far with regards the lifecycle of the AI System, especially since this has not yet been documented.	Further consideration under a renewed DPIA should be given once the Data AI Systems' lifecycles have been properly mapped. This will need to relate to non-personal data and results analyses as well, either via potential for reidentification or deductive disclosure, or for implications around integrity and risks for data that is not relatable back to individuals though may still pose wider data governance risks. An assessment based on a DPIA and perhaps a FRIA may assist.
How are we considering the privacy and data protection implications of the AI system's non-personal training-data or other processed non-personal data?	Arguably not	When considering the updated DPIA, IDERHA should also describe the non-personal data (i.e. data that does not relate to any person).
Are we aligning the AI system with relevant standards (e.g. ISO25, IEEE26) or widely adopted protocols for (daily) data management and governance?	Not explicitly - these have not yet been fully defined but this may need to be addressed. See comment under Documentation	As described under documentation, there is a specific need to catalogue where standards are being adhered to or will be as they are finalised towards the end of 2025
Are we considering the impact of the AI system on the right to privacy, the right to physical, mental and/or moral integrity and the right to data protection?	Yes - this forms part of the DPIA process and is being updated iteratively.	Further consideration for the operation of the AI components will be addressed in the updated DPIA, including consideration of anonymous / anonymised data sets and results of analyses.

Data Governance Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
Depending on the use case, are we establishing mechanisms that allow flagging issues related to privacy concerning the AI system?	There is an update and reporting procedure for changes in processing activity, but this has not yet entered into force as there are no data flows and operational system work per se as of yet	This process will need to be implemented as the algorithms are developed, models developed, and they are trained
Do partners involved with training and validation of algorithms have the right controls in place to use the data for training (i.e. privacy notice, consent where needed)	This is in part handled by the existing DPIA and Risk Management Framework	All materials should be re-reviewed to ensure they fall in line with new expectations.
Have these partners checked whether the purpose of processing the data through the AI system is in line with the initial purpose when the personal data was collected? If so, have they assessed whether further transparency is needed before processing the data, and if not, assess how to close the privacy gap to be able to process such data (i.e. re-consent, other means)?	This is in part handled by the existing DPIA and Risk Management Framework	These processes need to be checked again to ensure the appropriate standard has been reached in line with existing requirements through a new domain of processing,
Have the existing the lawful basis of personal data processing been assessed, and has there been careful consideration taken where legitimate interest will be used (as legitimate interest assessment for AI use may be more difficult)?	This is in part handled by the existing DPIA and Risk Management Framework	These need to be sanity checked by each partner and may be picked up during the DPIA update.
Have we considered performing a Pilot or Proof of Concept with a small quantity of personal data? If not, documenting the reason is advisable. POCs allow to detect errors and risks to data subjects to reassess the type of processing.	This has not yet been specifically identified however relates to the CNIL Guidelines on Artificial Intelligence and GDPR Compliance.	This can be further clarified in the assessment planning when it is reviewed.

DATA QUALITY CRITERIA

Table 6 provides details on the Data Quality Criteria that have been considered and still need to be addressed.

Table 6: Data Quality Criteria

Data Quality Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
From the AI Act – we must document and assess the following... Will we be able to?		
(a) the relevant design choices;	These are not yet fully articulated	A Catalogue of Design Choices is necessary for IDERHA as it proceeds - see details under documentation. This will be articulated around decisions on design and implementation, as well as areas of data analysis that led to any particular design decisions as part of documentation.
(b) data collection processes and the origin of data, and in the case of personal data, the original purpose of the data collection;	These are all collected and logged via the data flows and the DMP, DPIA and Ethics Committee approvals	Any amendments should be logged - though it is likely that the existing provisions meet the required standard.
(c) relevant data-preparation processing operations, such as annotation, labelling, cleaning, updating, enrichment and aggregation;	These are all collected and logged via the data flows and the DMP, DPIA and Ethics Committee approvals	Any amendments should be logged - though it is likely that the existing provisions meet the required standard.
(d) the formulation of assumptions, in particular with respect to the information that the data are supposed to measure and represent;	These have not been fully logged and will need to be updated	
(e) an assessment of the availability, quantity and suitability of the data sets that are needed;	These are all collected and logged via the data flows and the DMP, DPIA and Ethics Committee approvals	Any amendments should be logged - though it is likely that the existing provisions meet the required standard.
(f) examination in view of possible biases that are likely to affect the health and safety of persons, have a negative impact on fundamental rights or lead to discrimination prohibited under Union law, especially where data outputs influence inputs for future operations;	Bias assessments are being worked up as part of the data quality work.	Refer to Milestone 9 related to the data quality task explaining the data quality framework and how data quality assessments will need to be addressed. It remains unclear the extent to which data can be accessed as part of the assessment framework and this will need to be addressed.

<p>(g) appropriate measures to detect, prevent and mitigate possible biases identified according to point (f);</p>	<p>These have not yet been well defined</p>	<p>There are theoretical options described. But this is depending on the actual data. This needs from time to time to assess that the relevance and adequacy of the data continues to be updated. This will be aligned with the lifecycle specifications for data</p>
<p>(h) the identification of relevant data gaps or shortcomings that prevent compliance with this Regulation, and how those gaps and shortcomings can be addressed.</p>	<p>As part of the data quality work that is underway,</p>	<p>Our data quality framework is covering all requirements from the AI act (data should be complete, correct,). So if we accomplish line 25 and 26, line 27 should also be covered.</p>

BIAS AND REPRESENTATION CRITERIA

Table 7 provides an overview of the current state of IDERHA efforts to assess these, and what items will need to be implemented to meet expected compliance requirements.

Table 7: Bias and Representation Criteria

<p>Bias and Representation Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements</p>	<p>Response and Items to Implement for Compliance</p>
<p>Are we establishing a strategy or a set of procedures to avoid creating or reinforcing unfair bias in the AI system, both regarding the use of input data as well as for the algorithm design?</p>	<p>The milestone is covering this to certain extent. But I am eager to actually perform the assessment which would cover your text "the use of input data". Regarding the algorithm design, which this is more related to WP2. Refer also to the EMA Reflection paper on the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the medicinal product lifecycle</p>

Bias and Representation Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response and Items to Implement for Compliance
<p>How are we considering diversity and representativeness of end-users and/or subjects in the data?</p>	<p>Representativeness and diversity of subjects in the data (including the training data), is something which is covered in the milestone but needs to be turned into a practical assessment. Regarding representativeness of end-users, this is an interesting one. This is depending on the context we would use the algorithm most likely. This will likely form part of the WP2 Publication</p>
<p>Did you test for specific target groups or problematic use cases?</p>	<p>This has not yet been planned and needs to be reviewed.</p>
<p>Did you research and use publicly available technical tools, that are state-of-the-art, to improve your understanding of the data, model and performance?</p>	<p>Study Protocol describes which strategies will be used, evaluation plan how model performance will be assessed and after this there will be a publication draft that will contain all the details of the tooling to inform the modelling. It would be important to ascertain whether to find out if this is a requirement which we made at in our data quality assessment as well (on a more qualitative aspect).</p>

Bias and Representation Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response and Items to Implement for Compliance
<p>Did you assess and put in place processes to test and monitor for potential biases during the entire lifecycle of the AI system (e.g. biases due to possible limitations stemming from the composition of the used data sets (lack of diversity, non-representativeness)?</p>	<p>This is described in the Milestone. During data exploration phase the WP2 team try to understand the data and biases that might influence the modelling. This will be described in the publication draft. WP4 assesses the data quality and WP2 from the modelling perspective. These could be two different perspectives to look at the data. There might be certain differences in assessing the biases. These can be reconciled. For non-representativeness bias it is currently being created on Spanish data which means they are only represent ivies of those hospitals, not even for the whole of Spain. Certain biases are already included by virtue of partner appointment as part of initial phase of planning. This needs to be logged as well. (N.B. if you consider a model for Lung Cancer risk prediction, they are using models for cavity detection, and they will always have certain biases</p>
<p>Where relevant, did you consider diversity and representativeness of end-users and or subjects in the data?</p>	<p>As per answer above: Representativeness and diversity of subjects in the data (including the training data), is something which is covered in the milestone but needs to be turned into a practical assessment. Regarding representativeness of end-users, this is an interesting one. This is depending on the context we would use the algorithm most likely. This will likely form part of the WP2 Publication</p>

Bias and Representation Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response and Items to Implement for Compliance
Are we putting in place educational and awareness initiatives in addition to these workshops to help AI designers and AI developers be more aware of the possible bias they can inject in designing and developing the AI system?	This is not currently planned though the workshops are continuing and evolving
Are we establishing a mechanism that allows for the flagging of issues related to bias, discrimination or poor performance of the AI system?	This will need to be implemented as part of the evaluation frameworks and added to the Cataloguing Recommendations
Did you establish clear steps and ways of communicating on how and to whom such issues can be raised?	This has not yet been established and will need to be as part of the evaluation plans.
Did you identify the subjects that could potentially be (in)directly affected by the AI system, in addition to the (end-)users and/or subjects?	This relates to the information leaflets and protocols. Currently this is more for market authorisation outside of the research study context.
Is our definition of fairness commonly used and implemented in any phase of the process of setting up the AI system?	This has not yet been defined and will need to be considered as the systems are developed and tested.
Did you consider other definitions of fairness before choosing this one?	This has not yet been defined and will need to be considered as the systems are developed and tested.
Did you consult with the impacted communities about the correct definition of fairness, i.e. representatives of elderly persons or persons with disabilities?	This has not yet occurred and may form part of engagement activities in the future
Did you ensure a quantitative analysis or metrics to measure and test the applied definition of fairness?	IDERHA should align the Dat equality Milestone specifications to fairness considerations
Did you establish mechanisms to ensure fairness in your AI system?	IDERHA should align the Dat equality Milestone specifications to fairness considerations

Algorithm Training and Development Management

This section addresses Algorithm Training and development management as outlined below in tables 8 and 9 for data source and data analysis criteria.

Table 8: Data Source Criteria

Data Source Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
<p>Could the AI system cause critical, adversarial, or damaging consequences e.g. pertaining to human safety) in case of low reliability and/or reproducibility?</p>	<p>This is an area of risk management that has been partially covered by the DPIA and Ethics Oversight work, in terms of risks of harm to participants but also for any use inside a study. The risk prediction models and recommendations will need further consideration</p>	<p>IDERHA must ensure that the deployment of machine learning and trained algorithms does not cause harm and should update the DPIA framework with and review and potentially the addition of a FRIA</p>
<p>Did you put in place a well-defined process to monitor if the AI system is meeting the intended goals?</p>	<p>Process specification forms part of the study conduct, though it is not clear whether the platform development processes have been fully identified beyond the DoA and Milestones</p>	<p>Aligned with the AI System Lifecycle, the project should specify the goals and testing criteria aligned with a specified process for measuring success criteria and outcomes. This will likely be using defined test scenarios to address key cases in point for the use of the IDERHA platform across the different interventions. This is for the service providers and not the developers. Check with WP3 - WP1 is infrastructure and WP3 is more into the evaluation.</p>
<p>Did you test whether specific contexts or conditions need to be taken into account to ensure reproducibility?</p>	<p>This has not yet been fully defined</p>	<p>The algorithm testing needs to be established to indicate whether results are reproducible. This will include reference to the lifecycle. Partly this will be done by algorithm developers, measures are during the modelling you take care of certain tests to ensure the reproducibility. This is also relevant for service providers as well (check with WP3 and WP1).</p>

Data Source Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
Are we putting in place verification and validation methods and documentation (e.g. logging) to evaluate and ensure different aspects of the AI system's reliability and reproducibility?	This needs to be reviewed	Service providers to respond. They need to log the output of AI Models for patient data and input data.
Did you clearly document and operationalise processes for the testing and verification of the reliability and reproducibility of the AI system?	This needs to be reviewed	This will need to be established by WP2.
Are we defining tested failsafe fallback plans to address AI system errors of whatever origin and put governance procedures in place to trigger them?	This needs to be reviewed	This will depend on the system error - what are the system errors? More detail on what they might include. From the developers' perspective they might encounter a patient instance that might confuse the AI Model and then it generates certain errors. There could be other system errors but to address this case they should inform the user that the patient data confuses the model and the AI Model cannot answer a certain query. Would need to understand why the model was confused by the data and isolate where the issue is. This must be further specified as part of the testing plans across WP1, WP2 and WP3
Are we putting in place a proper procedure for handling the cases where the AI system yields results with a low confidence score?	This needs to be reviewed	Ai Model could provide a confidence score which essentially says how confident the model is for a certain prediction and this information should be provided to the user. The user can actually decide on its own whether to use the output or ignore what it says.
Will our AI system be using (online) continual learning?	Not sure yet... Depends on funding and future plans.	

Data Source Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
Did you consider potential negative consequences from the AI system learning novel or unusual methods to score well on its objective function?		

Table 9: Data Analysis Criteria

Data Analysis Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response and Items to Implement for Compliance
Could a low level of accuracy of the AI system result in critical, adversarial or damaging consequences?	There are a series of focal points for this aspect. One is deployment and operation; one is algorithm behaviour and one is Data Quality (including bias and fairness). Data quality aspect is important. Low quality of data could impact the AI system accuracy. Without quality regard this could well have an impact. See next comment and M9 work
Are we putting in place measures to ensure that the data (including training data) used to develop the AI system is up-to-date, of high quality, complete and representative of the environment the system will be deployed in?	Data quality is addressed in M9 as an overview in terms of requirements for completeness and quality. There are not yet specific measurements and tools to address the framework in the milestone. These will need to be developed and it has been discussed with WP2. Data Quality is not yet in the critical path and depends on having the data so the practical output has yet to be defined for the milestone. This will need to be put in the critical path. The milestone is here: https://lygatureprojectplaza.sharepoint.com/:w:/r/sites/IDERHA/Shared%20Documents/02.%20Work%20Packages/WP4%20Healthcare%20data%20standards%20and%20interoperability/Data%20Quality/IDERHA_M9.docx?d=w7618532d107c4bd5a40861d0b5892ee7&csf=1&web=1&e=mpIM0S

Data Analysis Criteria, Compliance Groups and Requirements	Response and Items to Implement for Compliance
<p>Are we putting in place a series of steps to monitor, and document the AI system's accuracy?</p>	<p>This is a matter for WP3 in particular as well as the publication work developed by WP2. This will also relate to the data quality framework in M9</p>
<p>Are we considering whether the AI system's operation can invalidate the data or assumptions it was trained on, and how this might lead to adversarial effects?</p>	<p>This is a matter for WP2's operational and assessment, as well as performance related aspects assessed by WP3. This will need to be considered as it may have inference for data accuracy and quality, potentially any assumptions made on the back of bias.</p>
<p>Are we putting processes in place to ensure that the level of accuracy of the AI system to be expected by end-users and/or subjects is properly communicated?</p>	<p>This is a matter for WP3. This is not explicitly stated in the data quality framework though the quality assessments will provide some evidence for communicating accuracy levels. This accuracy communication will be informed by understanding quality and bias in the training data and that will need to be fed into the assessments and evidence basis for informing users of accuracy within the system.</p>

Transparency – including Traceability, Human Oversight, Communications and Explainability as well as the outline of a Fundamental Rights Impact Assessment.

This section addresses the broad transparency groups: Traceability (Table 10) and Communications and Explainability (Table 12).

ACCOUNTABILITY AND TRACEABILITY

Table 10: Accountability and Traceability Criteria

Accountability and Traceability Criteria, Compliance and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
<p>How might we put in place measures that address the traceability of the AI system during its entire lifecycle?</p>	<p>This has not yet been fully defined This is a data quality dimension with regards documentation but if partners are harmonising data from three different sources this and the harmonisation process needs to be well documented. These are related to traceability and will assist with the traceability aspects that WP3 will need to assess. Refer to Cataloguing Recommendations</p>	<p>This will rely on the specification of the AI System Lifecycle and the linking of processes to data used in training as well as decision making. This will require looping back to original data (if not the individuals to whom the data relates)</p>

Accountability and Traceability Criteria, Compliance and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
<p>What measures can we put in place to continuously assess the quality of the input data to the AI system?</p>	<p>This needs further development</p>	<p>This will need to be reconciled with the existing milestones for Data Quality Assessments and updates along with the AI System Life Cycle. These will need to be reconciled for the blueprint implementation. Continuous monitoring has been outlined as a trustworthiness dimension and on this basis, it establishes the data harmonisation and source cataloguing data as a transparency matter. It implies that towards the biases understood from data sources. There is a consideration of representation in the data sets. This is currently a batch update at the moment and not continuous. WP2 input is needed for pipeline definition so that M9 can be updated and it can be automatically updated. Some of these categories can be a compliance check with documentation or would these checks be automated within the system? That has not yet been defined (and may need to be as part of the blueprint planning implementation). The M9 specs are based on the initial synthetic data generation pipeline. Will batch or continuous updates have an impact on the AI system operation? WP2 will need to assess. This goes to the assumptions question as specified above.</p>

Accountability and Traceability Criteria, Compliance and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
How can you trace back which data was used by the AI system to make a certain decision(s) or recommendation(s)?	This needs further development	The reconciliation will need to be defined as per the data quality and bias and the safety aspects described. This needs to be addressed along with the AI System Life Cycle. These will need to be reconciled for the blueprint
How can we trace back which AI model or rules led to the decision(s) or recommendation(s) of the AI system?	This needs further development	The reconciliation will need to be defined as per the data quality and bias and the safety aspects described. This needs to be addressed along with the AI System Life Cycle. These will need to be reconciled for the blueprint
What measures can we put in place to continuously assess the quality of the output(s) of the AI system?	This needs further development	The reconciliation will need to be defined as per the data quality and bias and the safety aspects described. This needs to be addressed along with the AI System Life Cycle. These will need to be reconciled for the blueprint implementation and assessments from WP3
How can we put adequate logging practices in place to record the decision(s) or recommendation(s) of the AI system?	This needs further development	The reconciliation will need to be defined as per the data quality and bias and the safety aspects described. This needs to be addressed along with the AI System Life Cycle. These will need to be reconciled for the blueprint implementation and assessments for WP1 and WP3.

COMMUNICATIONS AND EXPLAINABILITY

Table 11: Communications and Explainability

Communications and Explainability Criteria, Compliance and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
How can we communicate to users that they are interacting with an AI system instead of a human?	This is under consideration	It is not yet clear how the Platform components will address the declaration of AI involvement in the system, though it is unlikely that the Platform will operate like an assistant. Full declaration and transparency are advised, however, i.e. these recommendations were compiled by an AI System for notifications
How do we establish mechanisms to inform users about the purpose, criteria and limitations of the decision(s) generated by the AI system?	This is under consideration	It is not yet clear how the Platform components will address the declaration of AI involvement in the system, though it is unlikely that the Platform will operate like an assistant. Full declaration and transparency are advised, however, i.e. these recommendations were compiled by an AI System for notifications
Will we communicate the benefits of the AI system to users?	This is under consideration	This is already underway as part of the engagement strategies for public meetings, Advisory Boards and the Study Protocol and Consent Forms
Will we communicate the technical limitations and potential risks of the AI system to users, such as its level of accuracy and/ or error rates?	This is under consideration	This must be done as part of the study work where the benefits, risks and limitations need to be properly articulated as part of the development and deployment work
Will we provide appropriate training material and disclaimers to users on how to adequately use the AI system?	Yes - see comments in the other sections	

Communications and Explainability Criteria, Compliance and Requirements	Response	Items to Implement for Compliance
How can we explain the decision(s) of the AI system to the users?	This is under consideration	We need to specify the process for explaining decisions, likely under the same work to update details around the benefits and limitations of the systems and their use. We need to map out where this would apply,
Will we continuously survey the users if they understand the decision(s) of the AI system?	This is under consideration	This will need to be established with the ongoing monitoring approaches.

Sustainability

There are several key elements that relate to the onward sustainability of IDERHA and any tooling or services that it may choose to continue to develop after the end of the project. These are broadly captured below and the details relate to points that cannot yet be fully considered ahead of the implementation of the first round of development, or will need to be addressed later in the project on the back of some initial evidence gathering and implementation.

The key focus areas for criteria are Human Agency and Autonomy (Table 12), Accessibility and Universal Design (Table 13), Accessibility and Universal Design Criteria (Table 13), Stakeholder Participation (Table 14), Environmental and Societal Wellbeing (Table 15) and Impact on Work and Skills (Table 15).

Table 12: Human Agency and Autonomy Criteria

Human Agency and Autonomy Criteria, Compliance and Requirements	Responses	Items to Implement for Compliance
Is the AI system designed to interact, guide or take decisions by human end-users that affect humans or society?	Yes - clinical decisions may be impacted for patients, participant in the studies may make decisions based on AI Recommendations	
Could the AI system generate confusion for some or all end-users or subjects on whether a decision, content, advice or outcome is the result of an algorithmic decision?	This needs to be assessed	Along with the Lifecycle, we should include points of interaction for AI
Are end-users or other subjects adequately made aware that a decision, content, advice or outcome is the result of an algorithmic decision?	As already specified	
Could the AI system generate confusion for some or all end-users or subjects on whether they are interacting with a human or AI system?	Unlikely	Need to check as per interaction points above.
Are end-users or subjects informed that they are interacting with an AI system?	Specified already	Assess with interaction points above
Could the AI system affect human autonomy by generating over-reliance by end-users?	Unlikely	Need to check as per interaction points above.
Did you put in place procedures to avoid that end-users over-rely on the AI system?	Unlikely	Need to check as per interaction points above.

Human Agency and Autonomy Criteria, Compliance and Requirements	Responses	Items to Implement for Compliance
Could the AI system affect human autonomy by interfering with the end-user's decision-making process in any other unintended and undesirable way?	Unlikely	Need to check as per interaction points above.
Did you put in place any procedure to avoid that the AI system inadvertently affects human autonomy?	This is addressed in the Study protocol and updates	Need to check as per interaction points above.
Does the AI system simulate social interaction with or between end-users or subjects?	N/A	At least not yet
Does the AI system risk creating human attachment, stimulating addictive behaviour, or manipulating user behaviour? Depending on which risks are possible or likely, please answer the questions below:	Unlikely	Need to check as per interaction points above. This will be updated in the risk management tables for the DPIA and Project
Did you take measures to deal with possible negative consequences for end-users or subjects in case they develop a disproportionate attachment to the AI System?	TBD	Need to check as per interaction points above. This will be updated in the risk management tables for the DPIA and Project
Did you take measures to minimise the risk of addiction?	TBD	Need to check as per interaction points above. This will be updated in the risk management tables for the DPIA and Project
Did you take measures to mitigate the risk of manipulation?	TBD	Need to check as per interaction points above. This will be updated in the risk management tables for the DPIA and Project

Table 13: Accessibility and Universal Design Criteria

Accessibility and Universal Design Criteria, Compliance and Requirements	Responses and Items to Implement for Compliance
Did you ensure that the AI system corresponds to the variety of preferences and abilities in society?	TBC

Accessibility and Universal Design Criteria, Compliance and Requirements	Responses and Items to Implement for Compliance
Did you assess whether the AI system's user interface is usable by those with special needs or disabilities or those at risk of exclusion?	TBC
Did you ensure that information about, and the AI system's user interface of, the AI system is accessible and usable also to users of assistive technologies (such as screen readers)?	TBC
Did you involve or consult with end-users or subjects in need for assistive technology during the planning and development phase of the AI system?	TBC
Did you ensure that Universal Design principles are taken into account during every step of the planning and development process, if applicable?	TBC
Did you take the impact of the AI system on the potential end-users and/or subjects into account?	TBC
Did you assess whether the team involved in building the AI system engaged with the possible target end-users and/or subjects?	TBC
Did you assess whether there could be groups who might be disproportionately affected by the outcomes of the AI system?	TBC
Did you assess the risk of the possible unfairness of the system onto the end-user's or subject's communities?	TBC

Table 14: Stakeholder Participation Criteria

Stakeholder Participation Criteria, Compliance and Requirements	Responses	Items to Implement for Compliance
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<p>Did you consider a mechanism to include the participation of the widest range of possible stakeholders in the AI system's design and development?</p>	<p>There is a wealth of engagement activity across the project that addresses public audiences as well as internal project partners and Advisory Boards. Note the clinical acceptance aspects started to be considered at the CAB meeting on 12th February 2025.</p>	<p>We should document the engagement activities and catalogue them</p>
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Table 15: Societal and Environmental Wellbeing Criteria

Societal and Environmental Well-being Criteria, Compliance and Requirements	Responses and Items to Implement for Compliance
Environmental Well-being	TBC
Are there potential negative impacts of the AI system on the environment?	TBC
Which potential impact(s) do you identify?	TBC
Where possible, did you establish mechanisms to evaluate the environmental impact of the AI system's development, deployment and/or use (for example, the amount of energy used and carbon emissions)?	TBC
Did you define measures to reduce the environmental impact of the AI system throughout its lifecycle?	TBC

Table 16: Impact on Work and Skills Criteria

Impact on Work and Skills Criteria, Compliance and Requirements	Response and Items to Implement for Compliance
Does the AI system impact human work and work arrangements?	TBC
Did you pave the way for the introduction of the AI system in your organisation by informing and consulting with impacted workers and their representatives (trade unions, (European) work councils) in advance?	TBC
Did you adopt measures to ensure that the impacts of the AI system on human work are well understood?	TBC

Impact on Work and Skills Criteria, Compliance and Requirements	Response and Items to Implement for Compliance
Did you ensure that workers understand how the AI system operates, which capabilities it has and which it does not have?	TBC
Could the AI system create the risk of de-skilling of the workforce?	TBC
Did you take measures to counteract de-skilling risks?	TBC
Does the system promote or require new (digital) skills?	TBC
Did you provide training opportunities and materials for re- and up-skilling?	TBC
Impact on Society at large or Democracy	TBC
Could the AI system have a negative impact on society at large or democracy?	TBC
Did you assess the societal impact of the AI system's use beyond the (end-)user and subject, such as potentially indirectly affected stakeholders or society at large?	TBC
Did you take action to minimize potential societal harm of the AI system?	TBC
Did you take measures that ensure that the AI system does not negatively impact democracy?	TBC

Recommendations and Discussion

The assessment questions developed from the ALTAI and AI Act analysis provided indications around the key areas that need to be addressed from the organisational perspective through to the technical aspects for developers – the putative Providers and Deployers of the AI Systems that are under development. Key areas for attention are provided in this section as to what will be required to achieve compliance as the AI Act requirements are better understood.

Create a Catalogue that will support the organisational and technical requirements of IDERHA. Specifically the catalogue will include specification of the people responsible for assessment and validation, documentation of stakeholder engagement activities that relate to the wider trustworthiness and ethical requirements for compliance, how and when different stakeholders were able to comment and influence the development and prioritisation of the project, and the approach taken to address the user experience, results of the advisory and outputs of the system, and how these were handled. This catalogue can draw upon materials in the DMP and as the Catalogue is developed be referenced by the DMP.

The platform specifications, guidance document and technical documentation must also be developed. These aspects are still under development, but the compliance relies on being able to authoritatively point to

and provide these documents, instruction manuals and logging and evidentiary processes and resources as well as monitoring approaches aligned with the Lifecycle of the AI System needs to be recorded and catalogued. This in part will be addressed by the publication that WP2 is planning but will need to align with the other aspects as identified below.

A catalogue of data sources and uses will also be needed, which has already been specified in the Data Management Plan (and the Record of Processing Activity), Data Protection Impact Assessment and linked to local data provider cataloguing efforts.

Develop AI System and Data Lifecycle specification: the need to specify the expected lifecycle of the system is critical to several requirements for compliance. The lifecycle relates to the AI powered components of the platform as well as the other components that are impacted by them. It relates specifically to the training, development, update, operation and behaviour of the system overall, as well as the outputs of the system in terms of advisory or interaction. This also relates to the data feeds and inputs as part of the training and development processes.

This will help allow the risk management processes, including the DPIA, to be run at the different points in the lifecycles for data and the AI Systems. In particular the lifecycle development and risk management updates should refer in more detail to the [EMA reflection paper on the use of Artificial Intelligence \(AI\) in the medicinal product lifecycle](#) and the [CNIL guidelines for the development of AI Systems](#), as well as an ongoing consideration to adapt the DPIA approach and the DMP updates to the defined lifecycles for data and AI Systems,

Update the monitoring plans for the AI System: these span efforts across WP1, WP2 and WP3. WP1 must address the deployment specific monitoring that relate predominantly to the interaction of the system with other components, the security and robustness of the infrastructure and deployed services, and the interaction between the components.

WP2 focuses on the behaviours of the algorithms themselves, as well as the bias and impacts of the data (drawing on data quality and bias assessments led by WP4) on the behaviour of the algorithms. Specifically, WP2 is primarily responsible WP3 is responsible for the assessment of the developed system overall, building upon what has been developed for the Studies. The specific assessment criteria have been provided in the results section above and form the blueprint for compliance.

Define more clearly the AI components of the Platform and systems and specify the interaction points. This will help with the formal application of the results as specified above. The components themselves have been loosely defined in the specifications and the blueprint details above, but there needs to be a reconciliation with the finalised scope of the system and the interactions between the aspects. This will need to be added to the catalogue of technical documentation as outlined above.

Align the Data Quality Milestone Plans with the specific requirements of the AI Act and ALTAI. This will be an iterative process on the back of the definition of the AI driven components and the AI System Lifecycle. The areas where data quality and bias assessment should occur needs to be better specified across the data flow specifications and technical documentation.

Traceability of the AI decision making process and data used to inform decision is needed. This also includes tracing back to data used to train the AI Systems. The successful implementation of the traceability will depend on an adequate specification of the Lifecycle and the scope of the AI Components. Traceability will depend heavily on the record keeping and logging facilities across the platform and solution.

Logging and processes need to be established across the IDERHA solutions and platform operation. It is important to achieve this so that adequate record keeping and evidence can be retained to evaluate the operation of the AI components and their impact on the system as a whole, as per the AI Act and ALTAI requirements.

This will relate to the platform development and the specification of the components. It will also relate back to the AI System Lifecycle specification and a clear delineation of the assessment and record keeping responsibilities of each of the partners. The scope of logging and record keeping needs to be clearly defined between the development of the algorithms, the encapsulation within services, the deployment across infrastructure and the operation within that infrastructure. The DAISY tool at <https://elixir.pages.uni.lu/daisy-doc/> outlined above offers one potential solution to be explored.

Assessments for the operation and output of the system need to be reviewed and updated to include the blueprint requirements as outlined in the results section: this will relate back to the identification of each partner's work plan and the scope of the assessments that they need to address. It will also include a consideration as to whether the AI Models could be considered General Purpose (they currently do not meet the criteria).

Conduct a Fundamental Rights Impact Assessment that has been carefully scoped to cover IDERHA components and partners who are required to run a FRIA (public authorities primarily) but mindful that this will involve and include all partners. A key element of the FRIA is to articulate an easily understood, lay persons' guide to the systems and their operation. This lay guide will be key to the success of IDERHA and needs to be developed as part of the compliance requirements and existing engagements with stakeholders.

Enhance the Sustainability Plan where these criteria will take longer to focus in on as the platform and systems are developed. This will need to be considered later in the project.

Next Steps and Conclusions

This deliverable has listed the blueprint for trustworthy AI assurance and AI Act compliance as best as IDERHA can ascertain them. They have been developed based on a series of Webinars, workshops and research approaches to gather evidence from the risk management processes IDERHA has been engaged with from the project commencement, as well as an analysis and the development of an assessment framework based on the ALTAI and AI Act. Recommendations have been listed above and the path to implementing them will include:

- Specification of data processing and use and AS systems lifecycles (aligned with the EMA and CNIL recommendations around their specification and risk management).
- Provision of these recommendations in the development of the evaluation plans being handled by WP1, WP2 and WP3;
- Support in developing these plans and specifying the technical developments required, including standing agenda items at WP regular meetings and further engagement in ad hoc workshops;
- Deeper review of these recommendation at the May Annual Consortium Meeting where a dedicated workshop on AI Act roles is being planned and will be based on the recommendations applied herein.
- Update of the DPIA and where needed DMP with latest DMP version in focus and AI compliance requirements addressed and aligned to the data and system lifecycles specifications as well as a deeper consideration of data that is anonymous (specifically analysis data defining models and training requirements for algorithms).
- Conduct of a Fundamental Rights Impact Assessment (FRIA) led by WP5 after specifying the scope of the FRIA to the most applicable aspects of IDERHA (consider existing templates update using latest published practice post review);

The coming twelve months will prove critical for the implementation of these recommendations and the readiness of IDERHA and its solutions for compliance with the latest regulations. The approach should be adapted on the presentation of any new and pertinent guidance, standards or evidence basis for the specific implementation and validation requirements that the solution may focus on.